

SHAKESPEARE'S INFLUENCE ON OTHER AUTHORS

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Annotation: There is no doubt that Shakespeare has made a profound and lasting impact on the development of literature far beyond his native Britain. This unrivaled influence particularly extends to other overseas countries, where writers have long gleaned inspiration from Shakespeare's dramatic plays and verse. Most well-known writers have crossed vast distances of time and place to draw upon the universality of Shakespeare's themes, as well as the inventiveness of his language and forms, cultivating distinctly British modes of expression.

Shakespeare has had significant influence from the time of his death until today, in contemporary movies, plays, and poems. Many authors have been influenced and inspired by his works, and the phrases and words he has contributed to the English language.

The reason why Shakespeare has survived the test of time is due to what he writes and how he writes it. No one is better at summing up human emotions in simple, yet eloquent phrases. Shakespeare's stories surpass time and culture, which is why many authors continue to adapt them. Shakespeare's characters are like no other, particularly his tragic heroes. All of his characters are complex, Macbeth's good nature turns into greed and ambition because of his wife who convinces him to kill the King.

Many writers have admired and thus been influenced and inspired by Shakespeare. He has influenced many English poets, particularly Romantic poets such as Samuel Taylor Coleridge. In the late 17th century, English poet John Milton wrote a well-known epitaph on Shakespeare called "An Epitaph on the admirable Dramatic Poet, W. Shakespeare". This work appears in the Second Folio, the

1632 edition of William Shakespeare's works. In this work, Milton talks about Shakespeare's influence on him and his immortality:

Thou in our wonder and astonishment, Hast built thyself a live-long monument.

In the 18th century, there was Alexander Pope, one of the greatest poets of the Enlightenment. Pope wrote an edition of Shakespeare in 1725, with significant commentary. Pope also makes many references to Shakespeare in his many works.

Shakespeare has also influenced major novelists such as Herman Melville, Charles Dickens, Thomas Dickens and William Faulkner. Dickens uses many of Shakespeare's quotations throughout his works. Dickens has also derived at least twenty-five of his titles from Shakespeare.

Melville was even more influenced by Shakespeare. He used not only devices such as formal stage directions and extended soliloquies in *Moby-Dick*. Melville used the classic Shakespearean tragic figure, as his novel's main antagonist, Captain Ahab, a great man brought down by his faults.

Shakespeare influenced every generation of writers since his death and he continues to have an enormous impact on contemporary plays, movies, and poems. In the 19th century John Keats, one of the principle poets of the English Romantic Movement, was so greatly influenced by Shakespeare that every time Keats would write, he would keep Shakespeare's works next to him for inspiration and guidance.

In Keats's poems Shakespeare's style is replicated and plenty of his imagery is found. Keats never failed to mention his greatest role-model in personal letters to friends.

The Romantic poet, John Keats was so influenced by Shakespeare that he kept a bust of the Bard beside him while he wrote, hoping that Shakespeare would spark his creativity. Keats's poems duplicate Shakespeare's style and are full of Shakespearean imaginary.

In a letter to Benjamin Robert Haydon, dated 10 May 1817, Keats writes: "I remember your saying that you had notions of a good Genius presiding over you. I had the same thought – for things which I do half at Random are afterwards

confirmed by my judgement in a dozen features of Propriety. Is it too daring to fancy Shakespeare this Presider?”. It is interesting to note that George Bernard Shaw (1865-1950), who ridiculed those who worshipped Shakespeare (inventing an insulting term to denote the study of Shakespeare – bardolatry), secretly admired Shakespeare a great deal and often told his close friends that he thought the Bard had an unsurpassed command of the language.

Shakespeare’s influence is summarized nicely by Thomas Carlyle (albeit a bit over the top):

This King Shakespeare does not shine himself, in crowned sovereignty, over us all, as the noblest, gentlest, yet strongest of rallying-signs; indestructible; really more valuable in that point of view than any other means or appliance whatsoever? We can fancy him as radiant aloft over all Nations of Englishmen, thousand years hence. From Paramatta, from New York, wheresoever, under what sort of Parish-Constable soever, English men and women are, they will say to one another, ‘Yes, this Shakespeare is ours; we produced him, we speak and think by him; we are of one blood and kind with him. (Thomas Carlyle, *The Hero as Poet*, 1841).

Many authors have used phrases from Shakespeare’s works as titles for their own novels. Here is a list of just a few:

- *Brave New World* by Aldous Huxley (*The Tempest*, 5.1)
- *The Dogs of War* by Robert Stone (*Julius Caesar* 3.1)
- *The Winter of our Discontent* by John Steinbeck (*Richard III*, 1.1)
- *The Undiscovered Country* by Auther Schnitzer (*Hamlet*, 3.1)
- *Something Wicked this Way Comes* by Ray Bradbury (*Macbeth*, 4.1)
- *Bell, Book, and Candle* by John van Druten (*King John*, 3.3)

In 1899, Sir Herbert Beerbohm-Tree produced *King John*, the first movie based on a play by Shakespeare, and since then there have been dozens of movies and adaptations loosely based on Shakespeare’s work, including:

- *The Boys from Syracuse* (1940) – *The Two Gentlemen of Verona*
- *Joe Macbeth* (1953) – *Macbeth*
- *Kiss Me Kate* (1953) – *The Taming of the Shrew*

- Forbidden Planet (1956) – The Tempest
- Throne of Blood (1957) – Macbeth
- West Side Story (1961) – Romeo and Juliet
- Chimes at Midnight (1967) – various plays
- Ran (1985) – King Lear
- My Own Private Idaho (1991) – 1 Henry IV
- A Thousand Acres (1997) – King Lear
- 10 Things I Hate About You (1999) – The Taming of the Shrew
- Scotland, Pa. (2001) – Macbeth
- O (2001) – Othello

Shakespeare's writings continue impact new authors even today. Shakespeare is the most quoted writer in the history of the English-speaking world. Many of his quotations and neologisms have passed into everyday usage in English and other languages.

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